

INFLUENCE OF LOW TEMPERATURE ON ENERGY ABSORPTION IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES

Piyush K. Dutta and Karen J. L. Faran
U.S. Army Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory
Hanover, New Hampshire 03755

David Hui
University of New Orleans
New Orleans, Louisiana 70148

ABSTRACT

This work focused, over a wide temperature range, on the behavior of quasi-isotropic graphite/epoxy laminates subjected to an extremely short duration (140-microseconds) stress wave impact from a hemispherical indenter of a Hopkinson pressure bar apparatus. Energy absorption by the laminates was determined by using elementary stress wave propagation theory and the incident, reflected, and transmitted stress wave forms. The impacted laminates were then C-scanned to determine the extent of the damage resulting from the impact. Temperature influence on energy absorption at different impact velocities was determined and related to the micro mechanics of the laminates. The experimental results were compared with the results from numerical analysis using a modified version of the 3DIMPACT finite element code. The influence of low temperature and resulting matrix stiffening on energy absorption in the Hertzian deformation domain (low velocity) is predictable by the numerical analysis and is supported qualitatively by the experimental results.

Keywords: Composites, Energy absorption, High strain rate, Hopkinson bar, Impact, Low temperature, Projectile impact, and Stress wave.

INTRODUCTION

Most literature dealing with energy absorption in laminated composites describes the use of dropweight or pendulum impact test apparatus. In these techniques, energy absorption is determined by subtracting the residual kinetic energy from the initial energy. Thus, the effects of stress wave propagation, which is a source of damage initiation, cannot be examined using these testing techniques. Furthermore, it is difficult to measure the laminate's energy absorption during the penetration process, the projectile's velocity, the contact force, and the duration of impact. A modified Hopkinson bar testing technique developed by Dutta et al. (1991) eliminates these restrictions and allows a thorough examination of the projectile impact process.

The experimental effort described in this report involved an analytical and experimental study of energy absorption within graphite/epoxy plates impacted by a hemispherical-nosed impactor attached to a split Hopkinson bar test apparatus. The work is novel in that the plate's energy absorption was accurately measured using the recorded incident, reflected, and transmitted stress waves. The Hopkinson bar test apparatus allowed determination of velocity, force, and energy absorption during the entire impact duration. Thus the setup allowed "controlled" testing, capable of determining the energy absorption of

impacted composite specimens. The only limitation was that the impactor was forced into the laminate at relatively low velocities.

Experimental results, obtained over a wide temperature range, were compared with numerical results obtained by using a modified version of 3DIMPACT, a finite element code developed (Choi and Chang, 1990) to predict the damage in composite plates subjected to low-velocity foreign object impact. The material parameters in the models were selected to match as closely as possible the specimens used in the Hopkinson pressure bar apparatus experiments. However, the clamping condition and the geometry of the plates were different from the Hopkinson bar specimen. The experiments were conducted on circularly clamped plates, whereas the numerical analysis was done with a rectangular configuration of the plates. The current version of the code did not allow the circular configuration without any major modification. At the initial stage of this investigation it was of interest to examine whether temperature reduction results in the similar decrease in energy absorption, as observed from the Hopkinson bar experiments even when the geometrical configuration of clampings was different.

Provided first in this paper is a synopsis of the Hopkinson bar apparatus measurements done by Dutta et al. (1991). The results from the finite element modeling and a comparison between the experimental and numerical results follow in the next section.

RESULTS OF THE HOPKINSON PRESSURE BAR APPARATUS

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the modified Hopkinson bar apparatus: the striker, the incident bar, the laminate panel clamping assembly, and the transmitter bar. The transmitter bar is free to slide forward or backward. As the striker (1) hits the incident bar (2) and drives the indenter into the laminated plate, the plate bends and behaves like a spring-mass system.

The theoretical wave mechanics involved in the impact process discussed are based on elementary principles of unidirectional stress wave propagation. The impact produced by the striker bar on the

Figure 1. Schematic of the modified Hopkinson bar test setup.

Hopkinson bar persists for a few hundred microseconds, and a small but finite time is required for the effects of the impact force (stress wave) to enter the graphite epoxy test laminate at the opposite end of the bar. Upon entering the laminate, a portion of the incident stress wave is propagated into the transmitter bar (3), and another portion is reflected back into the incident bar. Incident, reflected, and transmitted stress waves are measured by strain gauge instruments, as described by Dutta et al. (1987).

Wave mechanics within this system was analyzed to determine the force-displacement relationship between the impactor and the composite laminate. The energy absorbed during the process was also determined as a function of time and impact velocity. The velocity, force, and energy absorbed were calculated from incident, reflected, and transmitted wave forms. There is further discussion of wave mechanics in the Hopkinson pressure bar apparatus in Dutta et al. (1991).

In the current study, the laminate specimens consisted of 30 plies of AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy with the following stacking sequence:

$$\left[(\pm 45/0_2)_2 / 90 / \pm 45 / 0_2 / \pm 45 \right]_S \quad (1)$$

Test panels were clamped around the edges so that a circular area faced the incident bar, and the indenter was driven into the laminate by the force of the incident bar's stress wave. The laminate was considered to be quasi-isotropic, with the following properties:

$$\begin{aligned} E_r &= \text{Young's modulus across specimen face} \\ &= 51.16 \text{ GPa (7.42 Msi)} \\ E_z &= \text{Young's modulus across specimen thickness} \\ &= 11.86 \text{ GPa (1.72 Msi)} \\ \rho &= \text{density} \\ &= 1522.4 \text{ kg/m}^3 \\ c_z &= \text{pressure wave speed through specimen thickness} \\ &= 3.043 \text{ km/s} \end{aligned}$$

The Hopkinson bars used in the tests had the following parameters:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \text{area} = 1140 \text{ mm}^2 (1.7675 \text{ in}^2) \\ c &= \text{wave speed} = 5.017 \text{ km/s (197,531 in./s)} \\ E &= \text{Young's modulus} = 193.05 \text{ GPa (28 Msi)} \end{aligned}$$

The wave propagates as a compressive wave through the thickness of the plate with the wave speed, c_z , and eventually reflects off the rear (free) surface as a tensile wave with the same velocity. During the duration of the stress wave there are five stages of interaction between the indenter and the plate. These stages are described by the results of force and velocity history measurements shown in Figure 2. The five stages involved in the penetration process are:

1. *Initial loading stage:* ($0 < t < t_1$), The indenter accelerates into the plate, as can be seen from the increasing slope of the velocity slope (curve D).

2. *Initial unloading stage:* ($t_1 < t < t_2$), The indenter force decreases rapidly and the corresponding velocity increases at a slower rate. The drop in the indenter force is attributed to damage either in the contact region or near the rear surface due to a reflected tensile wave. Although invisible on the surface, interior damages near the rear surface, possibly caused by the reflected stress wave were detected by C-scan of the specimens tested in the Hopkinson bar. Figure 3 shows the interior damage of one of the test plates. The reflected tensile wave may cause the plate to move away from the indenter, thus reducing the contact force.

Figure 2. Results of force, velocity, and strain history measurements.

Figure 3. C-scan results showing interior damage of the plates from Hopkinson bar impact.

3. *Constant velocity stage:* ($t_2 < t < t_3$), The indenter and the plate both move at almost the same velocity, indicating that there is no interfacial contact force.

4. *Separation stage:* ($t_3 < t < t_4$), A gap may indeed occur at this stage between the plate and the indenter, and the indenter experiences a tensile force. (Note a reversal of the force direction in curve C.)

Figure 4. Bar stresses and energy absorption history.

5. *Vibration stage*: ($t_4 < t < t_5$), During this stage the plate exerts an oscillating force on the indenter where contact may be lost and regained many times.

Figure 4 shows the cumulative energy absorption and the bar stresses as functions of time. The amount of absorbed energy increases rapidly with time when the indenter accelerates into the plate and during the initial unloading stage, where the indenter force decreases rapidly. When the velocities become constant, there is very little contact force, and the absorbed energy increases more slowly. During the plate separation stage, a portion of the energy returns to the incident bar as the indenter accelerates into the free space in front of it. This energy is subtracted from the cumulative energy, and so the curve dips at this stage. The energy absorbed during the final stage is constant and is the energy that causes plate damage.

Figure 5 shows the laminate's energy absorption, E_A , versus the maximum velocity of the indenter. The data follows the relationship

$$E_A = n V^m \quad (2)$$

where the exponent m is found to be 2.55 for room temperature (21°C) and 4.53 for low temperature (-30°C). The value of the constant n is 3.75×10^{-5} for 21°C and 1.01×10^{-9} for -30°C.

Tests by Nishijima and Okada (1982) demonstrated that a reduction in temperature causes a reduction in impact strength. Therefore, for a given impact velocity, more damage occurs at lower temperatures and more energy is absorbed. The experimental data in Figure 5 show this trend after a transition velocity of about 4.8 m/s (190 in./s). Above this velocity, more energy is absorbed by specimens held at low temperature. Below this transition velocity, the low temperature has an opposite effect.

In the low velocity range, the Hertzian contact force is the most dominating energy absorption mechanism among the nonrecoverable energies. This energy is a function of the Young's modulus of the composite plate in the thickness direction (Greszczuk, 1982), and is therefore influenced at low temperature by the change in elastic modulus of the resin matrix (Dutta et al., 1991). As the temperature is reduced, the value of the Hertzian contact energy decreases. The experimental results shown in Figure 5 confirm this.

In brief, low temperature influences the energy absorption characteristics and control the damage mechanisms. At low temperatures, existence of a transition velocity was also observed. Above this

Figure 5. Influence of temperature and velocity on energy absorption.

velocity, energy absorption from an impact is higher than at room temperature. In addition, at lower temperatures the laminate absorbs less energy, and the reduced impact strength causes a larger volume of damage below the transition velocity.

RESULTS FROM 3DIMPACT

Modeling parameters

3DIMPACT is a finite element program designed to predict damage in composite plates subjected to low-velocity foreign object impact (Figure 6) (Choi and Chang, 1990). Analysis includes calculating stress distributions inside the laminates during impact and also predicting matrix failure and delamination growth. The material in each layer is treated as though it were homogeneous and orthotropic.

The impactor is also modeled as an elastic body with a spherical nose that, when contacting the panel with relative indentation depth a , develops

Figure 6. Schematic of 3DIMPACT setup.

a force distribution determined by the Hertzian contact law, as modified by Sun and Yang (1980):

$$F = K \alpha^{1.5}, \quad (3)$$

$$K = \frac{4}{3} \sqrt{r} \left[\frac{1}{(1 - \nu_s^2)/E_s + 1/E_{yy}} \right], \quad (4)$$

where r , ν_s and E_s are the local radius, the Poisson's ratio, and the Young's modulus of the impactor, respectively. E_{yy} is the transverse modulus normal to the fiber direction.

3DIMPACT models transverse impact of the panels by a low-velocity spherical nosed projectile, and the program determines the velocity required for damage initiation, extent of delamination, and the effects of ply orientation and thickness on the damage. The matrix crack and delamination growth criteria were based on the analysis by Choi and Chang (1990). The code was modified at CRREL so temperature dependence of the material properties could be included in the model. The influences of temperature on the properties were determined by experimental investigation at CRREL and have been reported in various publications (Dutta, 1992a, 1992b). Table 1 summarizes the change of properties in relation to temperature used in the model.

Instead of considering circular specimens as in the Hopkinson bar experiments, 3DIMPACT calculates the damage of rectangular plates. The boundary conditions were picked such that the four sides of the plate were clamped. The plates used measured 10 mm × 10 mm (3.9 in. × 3.9 in.).

Table 1. Temperature dependence of material properties.

Property	Room temperature property	Derived property for temperature change
Longitudinal Young's modulus	$E_{xx}(T_0)$	$E_{xx}(T) = E_{xx}(T_0)$
Transverse Young's modulus	$E_{yy}(T_0)$	$E_{yy}(T) = E_{yy}(T_0) + 20 \times 10^6(T_0 - T)$
Poisson's ratio in the x - y direction	$\nu_{xy}(T_0)$	$\nu_{xy}(T) = \nu_{xy}(T_0)$
Poisson's ratio in the y - z direction	$\nu_{yz}(T_0)$	$\nu_{yz}(T) = \nu_{yz}(T_0)$
Shear modulus in the x - y direction	$G_{xy}(T_0)$	$G_{xy}(T) = G_{xy}(T_0) + 3.8 \times 10^6(T_0 - T)$
Ply thickness	$H(T_0)$	$H(T) = H(T_0)$
Density	$\rho(T_0)$	$\rho(T) = \rho(T_0)$
Critical indentation	$ACR(T_0)$	$ACR(T) = ACR(T_0)$
Longitudinal tensile strength	$LT(T_0)$	$LT(T) = LT(T_0) \left[\frac{E_{yy}(T_0)}{E_{yy}(T_0) + 20 \times 10^6(T_0 - T)} \right]^{0.5}$
Longitudinal compressive strength*	$LC(T_0)$	$LC(T) = 2V_f \left\{ \frac{V_f E_{xx}(T_0) [E_{yy}(T_0) + 20 \times 10^6(T_0 - T)]}{3(1 - V_f)} \right\}^{0.5}$
Transverse tensile strength	$TT(T_0)$	$TT(T) = TT(T_0) + 0.4 \times 10^6(T_0 - T)$
Transverse compressive strength	$TC(T_0)$	$TC(T) = TC(T_0) + 0.4 \times 10^6(T_0 - T)$
Iosipescu shear strength	$IS(T_0)$	$IS(T) = IS(T_0) + 3.8 \times 10^6(T_0 - T)$

* $V_f = 0.6$, volume fraction

The stacking sequence of the material was identical to that of the experiments conducted with the Hopkinson bar apparatus, but the material selected was CFRP AS/3501, which has the following ply properties at room temperature:

- E_{xx} = longitudinal Young's modulus = 138 GPa (20.01 Msi)
- E_{yy} = transverse Young's modulus = 8.96 GPa (1.30 Msi)
- ν_{xy} = Poisson's ratio in the x - y direction = 0.3
- ν_{yz} = Poisson's ratio in the y - z direction = 0.3
- G_{xy} = shear modulus in x - y direction = 7.10 GPa (1.30 Msi)
- H = ply thickness = 1.25×10^{-4} m
- ρ = density = 1.60×10^3 kg/m³
- ACR = critical indentation = 8.03×10^{-5} m
- LT = longitudinal tensile strength = 1.45 GPa (0.21 Msi)
- LC = longitudinal compressive strength = 1.45 GPa (0.21 Msi)
- TT = transverse tensile strength = 52.0 MPa (7.54 ksi)
- TC = transverse compressive strength = 206 MPa (29.9 ksi)
- IS = Iosipescu shear strength = 92.9 MPa (13.47 ksi)

The impactor used was a steel ball of 0.842×10^{-2} kg mass, 0.635×10^{-2} radius, Young's modulus of 210 GPa, and Poisson's ratio of 0.3. Velocities in the model matched those of the Hopkinson bar measurements.

Because the sample shapes and materials of the Hopkinson bar apparatus and numerical modeling were not identical, it is not possible to make quantitative comparisons between the two sets of results. Instead, one may observe the similarities in the behavior of the materials, due to change in velocity and temperature.

Figure 7. Influence of temperature and velocity on energy absorption, as calculated by 3DIMPACT.

Figure 7 shows the energy absorbed against the maximum velocity, as calculated by 3DIMPACT, for temperatures of 24°C, -30°C, and -60°C. Comparison of Figures 5 and 7 shows that the numerical results are in agreement only qualitatively with those of the Hopkinson bar apparatus. The transition velocity seems to occur at around 5.6 m/s (220 in./s), which is higher than the value observed in the experiments. The lack of quantitative agreement is somewhat expected because of the different geometric configuration of the specimens and their sizes.

The numerical data also follows the relationship given in Equation 2, with values of n and m for the different temperatures given in Table 2. Note that the results are consistent with those from the experiment in that the value of n decreases as the temperature decreases, and the value of m increases with decreasing temperature.

Table 2. Curve parameters for 3DIMPACT results of energy vs. velocity.

Temperature (°C)	n	m
50	2.41×10^{-5}	1.78
24	2.99×10^{-5}	1.74
-30	1.73×10^{-5}	1.84
-60	1.57×10^{-5}	1.86
-100	1.37×10^{-5}	1.88
-150	6.71×10^{-6}	2.02

CONCLUSIONS

A low-velocity impact testing of composite with an instrumented Hopkinson bar apparatus was performed, and the impact force history following the direct material characteristics was measured. The energy loss during impact is a direct measure of the damage, and the modified Hopkinson bar allows this direct measurement.

Two important materials characteristics control the damage energy: temperature and rate-sensitivity (velocity). Both the Hopkinson bar experimental data and the 3DIMPACT numeric analysis data prove this.

Internal damage from even low-velocity impact can be extensive and significant, as shown by the C-scan data of the laminates.

It is unfortunate that the material, shape, size, and clamping configuration of the experimental laminated plate were different from the numeric model parameters, which resulted in energy absorption values significantly different between the two approaches. However, the influence of low temperature on the energy absorption showed the same trend for both. It is the matrix stiffness increase at low temperature that causes Hertzian deformation energy decrease at low velocities.

At relatively higher velocities it is the reduction of impact strength at low temperatures that causes a greater volume of damage and therefore larger energy loss.

More research is needed to analyze failure behavior through the transition zone from Hertzian deformation to through-the-thickness penetration.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Dr. Dutta and Capt. Faran performed this work as a part of the project on cold region technology funded by the U.S. Army Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory and the U.S. Air Force Flight Dynamics Laboratory at Wright-Patterson Air Force Base. Dr. Hui was supported completely by the U.S. Air Force. They would like to thank Ms. M.R. Altamirano for her help in designing the modification of the Hopkinson bar impact facility.

REFERENCES

1. Dutta, P.K., Hui, D., and Altamirano, M.R., *Energy Absorption of Graphite/Epoxy Plates Using Hopkinson Bar Impact*, USA Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory, CRREL Report 91-20, 1991.
2. Choi, H., and Chang, F., *Effect of Traverse Low-Velocity Impact on Graphite/Epoxy Laminated Composites*, Final Report to U.S. Army Research Office, Contract No. DAALO3-87-K-0115 by Stanford University, 1990.
3. Dutta, P.K., Farrell, D., and Kalafut, J., *The CRREL Hopkinson Bar Apparatus*, USA Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory, Special Report 87-24, 1987.
4. Nishijima, S. and Okada, T., Charpy Impact Test of Cloth Reinforced Epoxide Resin at Low Temperature, *Nonmetallic Materials and Composites at Low Temperatures* (G. Hartwig and D. Evans, Eds.), Plenum Press, New York, 1982, pp. 259–275.
5. Greszczuk, L.B., *Damage in Composite Materials Due to Low Velocity Impact*, Chapter 3 in *Impact Dynamics* (J. A. Zukas et al., Eds.), John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1982, pp. 55–94.
6. Sun, C.T., and Yang, S. H., *Contact Law and Impact Responses of Laminated Composites*, NASA CR-159884, National Aeronautical and Space Administration, Washington, D.C., 1980.
7. Dutta, P.K., *Tensile Strength of Unidirectional Fiber Composites at Low Temperatures*, *Proceedings of the 6th Japan-U.S. Conference on Composite Materials, Orlando, Florida*, 1992a.
8. Dutta, P.K., *Low Temperature Compressive Strength of Glass-Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composites*, *Journal of Off-Shore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering*, 1992b (to be published).